

Paper Club Report: Beyond Herd Immunity Against Strategic Attackers

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Abstract—This report is based on the paper titled “Beyond Herd Immunity Against Strategic Attackers.” [1] investigates network models and various methods to mitigate strategic attacks in networks. It also emphasizes the role of herd immunity, and herd mentality in enhancing system robustness.

Index Terms—strategic attackers, herd immunity, cybersecurity, and network defense.

I. INTRODUCTION

Herd immunity [2] has been foundational in network epidemics. Herd mentality occurs when many devices in a network are immune and are protecting the remaining devices from malware by reducing their exposure. However, this is an advantage to strategic attackers who actively search for vulnerable nodes. The traditional understanding of herd immunity assumes passive infections, not accounting for attackers targeting specific weaknesses. This report reviews [1] proposed by Rufino et al. to address this gap and examine how strategic attackers change the landscape of cybersecurity risks.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

- 1) Compute infection probabilities based on infection rates.
- 2) Determine the equilibrium in the system considering the cost of countermeasures and infection risks.

This perspective emphasizes the importance of understanding both the dynamic nature of malware and the strategic decisions needed to protect networks effectively.

III. RELATED WORK ANALYSIS

Epidemic models [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8] in computer networks encompasses both endogenous and exogenous infections. The traditional models, such as the [9] Susceptible-Infected-Susceptible (SIS) model are instrumental in analyzing malware spread, and in capturing short-term and evolving infection dynamics while treating infections as passive rather than strategic. [10] foundational work on biological systems has been complemented by studies like [11], which consider economic incentives [12] behind cyberattacks.

Recent research [13], [14] highlights the role of strategic attackers in epidemic modeling, with a focus on botnets and continuously evolving malware vulnerabilities. However, little attention has been given to economic-constrained attackers from an epidemic perspective. [1] highlights the gap regarding how attackers can allocate limited resources while exploiting network vulnerabilities that traditional herd immunity models overlook.

IV. STRATEGIC ATTACKERS AND NETWORK SECURITY

Modern cybersecurity threats, such as botnets, and DDoS attacks rely on active scanning and searching for weak devices in the network. [15] These Botmasters can exploit both endogenous infections and exogenous infections. Attackers can [16] also leverage tools such as port scanning to specifically locate vulnerable nodes, which challenges the effectiveness of herd immunity. An important point made by the [1] is that all nodes must adopt countermeasures even when the majority of

the network is already protected, as attackers will focus on the [1] easy targets.

V. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

[1] puts a detailed framework for how infections spread in a network and how vaccination strategies counter infections. The paper focuses on critical components such as network nodes, infection types, and the costs of applying these protective measures.

A. Terminology

This section explains the key terms and concepts, as summarized in Table I. The table provides an overview of the entire network setup.

B. User Population, Cost Function, and Network Topology

The [1] model defines a network consisting of M nodes, of which N are vulnerable to infection. The remaining nodes are vaccinated and immune. Vulnerable nodes undergo an epidemic process involving infection, recovery, and potential reinfection.

Cost Function: A node's cost depends on its vaccination status. Vaccinated nodes incur a relative cost C , while unvaccinated nodes face a cost proportional to their infection rate ρ .

Network Topology: The infections spread is shown by the adjacency matrix A , which represents the connections between nodes. The network structure determines how effectively infections spread through endogenous means.

C. Threat Model

The attacker's power is modeled by the infection rate λ , which controls the number of infections an attacker can issue per time unit. This exogenous infection rate depends on the size of the vulnerable population N and the attacker's total budget.

D. Epidemic Infection and Recovery

Vulnerable nodes can alternate between two states: susceptible and infected. The duration in the infected state is modeled using an exponential distribution governed by the recovery rate μ . Infection can arise either from infected neighbors or from external attackers.

Infection Rate: The infection rate is the product of the exogenous infection rate λ and the endogenous infection rate γd , where d is the number of infected neighbors.

VI. ANALYTICAL MODEL

The core of the [1] research paper is the analytical model that captures the relation between strategic attackers and the network. Unlike traditional SIS (susceptible-infected-susceptible) models used in epidemiology, the [1] model accounts for the attacker's limited infection budget and the balance between exogenous and endogenous infection rates.

- **Endogenous Infection Rate (γ):** Represents the infection rate from neighbors.
- **Exogenous Infection Rate (λ):** Denotes the infection rate from external, strategic attackers, determined by the number of vulnerable nodes (N).

The model shows that infection probabilities evolve in two stages: The probabilities decrease as more nodes become vulnerable, with exogenous infections being the dominant factor. The probabilities increase as endogenous infections take over. This non-linear equilibrium, as described in [1], suggests that even a small number of unvaccinated devices can become easy targets for infection.

VII. VACCINATION GAME AND EQUILIBRIA

The paper [1] proposes the concept of a vaccination game where each node in the network decides whether or not to invest in heavy protective measures based on the infection probability and the vaccination cost. In equilibrium analysis, two scenarios are highlighted:

- **Follow-the-crowd:** Nodes vaccinate as infection rates remain high.
- **Avoid-the-crowd:** Nodes avoid vaccination when most of the network is protected but remain at risk from strategic attackers.

The equilibrium dynamics indicate that infection probabilities can stabilize at two points: a stable equilibrium where nodes maintain protection, and Unstable equilibrium where countermeasures are abandoned.

The system can become highly unstable in the case of an unstable equilibrium, where infection rates may escalate if countermeasures are abandoned. This highlights the delicate balance between the cost of vaccination and the risk of infection.

TABLE I
TERMINOLOGY OVERVIEW

Term	Description
Network Setup	Nodes: Devices/users in the network. Vaccinated Nodes: Immune due to strong security measures. Vulnerable Nodes: Have light or no protection.
Vaccination Types	Heavyweight Vaccination: Strong security measures (e.g., quarantine, anti-virus). Lightweight Vaccination: Basic defenses (e.g., anti-virus updates).
Node States	Susceptible: Prone to infection. Infected: Can recover but remain vulnerable.
Infection Probability	The likelihood of a vulnerable node being infected, influenced by infection and recovery rates.
Types of Infections	Endogenous: Spread from neighboring infected nodes. Exogenous: Attacks from external sources (limited attack budget).
Costs Involved	Vaccination Cost (V): Cost of securing a node. Infection Cost (H): Higher cost incurred when infected. Relative Vaccination Cost (C = V/H): Ratio determining security investment.
Attacker's Budget	Limited resources for attackers, distributed across vulnerable nodes, affecting attack frequency.

VIII. MODEL ANALYSIS

The analysis focuses on the model's equilibrium points and how infection probabilities evolve with the network size. The model identifies specific points where the infection probability reaches equilibrium.

A. Random Vulnerable Nodes

In a scenario where nodes are randomly selected as vulnerable, the analysis reveals a critical population size where infection probability is minimized. This helps inform strategies for determining how many nodes need to be vaccinated to protect the network.

B. Closed-Form Approximation

To simplify the assessment of equilibrium points, the paper [1] uses the NAM [17] & Lambert W function [18] to approximate infection probabilities. This method compromises some accuracy, however, it provides a quick and efficient way to understand infection dynamics.

IX. SIMULATION AND VALIDATION

The paper [1] simulates their theoretical model using malware like the [19] Mirai botnet to gauge the practical implications of the proposed model. Results validate that the two-regime behavior predicted by the [1] model: initial infection rates decrease as attackers' focus is divided among many

vulnerable nodes, but eventually increase as endogenous infections gain prominence. These results help quantify the impact of parameters like the exogenous infection rate (λ) and up-time of nodes.

X. BROADER IMPLICATIONS

This work extends the traditional understanding of network immunity by focusing on the behavior of strategic attackers and highlights important considerations for system defense strategies as exhibit herd immunity: The model can help insurers assess risks associated with residual vulnerabilities in networks that exhibit herd immunity.

XI. CONCLUSION

The paper [1] proposes a new epidemic model that accounts for strategic attackers targeting weak vulnerable nodes. Unlike traditional models, [1] considers attacker behavior and [20] resource limitations, which leads to a realistic perspective on security threats. The model, also demonstrates that the infection probabilities follow a two-regime behavior. This dynamic highlights the need for adaptive cybersecurity strategies. The proposed [1] vaccination game shows that traditional approaches to herd immunity are not sufficient against strategic attackers. In conclusion, this model is effective for understanding and mitigating cybersecurity threats in networked systems.

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